

Reduction of periodate ion by *o*-anisidine – Application for microgram determination of periodate

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Abstract : The progress of Mn^{II} catalysed reduction of periodate by *o*-anisidine in acetone-water medium was followed by monitoring the increase in the absorbance of reaction intermediate. The reaction was found to be first order with respect to catalyst, substrate and oxidant each. The main reaction product characterized on the basis of melting point and spectroscopic studies, is methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone. The effect of pH, dielectric constant of medium and free radical scavengers were studied to develop the best fit conditions for developing a new and simple kinetic-spectrophotometric method for microgram determination of periodate in the range 3.82 to 101.72 µg/mL. The characteristics of various calibration curves, percentage recovery, effect of interferrants, correlation coefficient and comparison with other reported methods are presented.

Keywords : Microgram estimation, periodate ion, *o*-anisidine, Mn^{II} catalysed, methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone.

Introduction

A perusal of literature reveals that many methods¹⁻¹⁶ that have been reported for determination of periodate ion alone or in combination with iodate are based on techniques such as spectrophotometry, pulse polarography, fluorometry, chemiluminescence measurement, chromatography, potentiometry, and IR spectroscopy etc. and suffer from a complicated pre-treatment of samples, complex operation and use of costly equipments. Although there are some reports available in literature related to the Mn^{II} catalysed/uncatalysed periodate oxidation of aromatic amines¹⁷⁻³⁴, these reactions have not been explored for estimation of periodate. Present paper deals with a new and simple kinetic-spectrophotometric method developed by us for microgram determination of periodate based on its Mn^{II} catalysed reduction by *o*-anisidine (ANIS).

Experimental

Reagents :

Sodium metaperiodate (Loba Chemie), *o*-anisidine (Aldrich), acetone (E. Merck), manganese sulphate monohydrate (Aldrich) and all other chemicals of analytical

reagent/guaranteed reagent grade were used after redistillation/recrystallization. Triply distilled water was used for preparation of the solutions. Thiel, Schultz and Koch buffer³⁵ was used for maintaining the pH.

Recommended kinetic-spectrophotometric procedure :

The reaction mixture turned light yellow to wine-red, thereafter brown followed by precipitation. The reaction was studied in a spectrophotometric cell and initiated by adding temperature equilibrated NaIO₄ solution of known concentration to the reaction mixture containing the ANIS, Mn^{II} and buffer and maintained at the desired temperature (± 0.1 °C). The progress of the reaction was followed by recording the absorbance on Shimadzu double beam spectrophotometer (UV-2550), at 490 nm, i.e. the λ_{max} of the reaction mixture. λ_{max} was not found to change with change in time under experimental conditions (Fig. 1). Desired temperature was maintained with the help of a high precision thermostatic control.

Following are the finally worked out conditions for running the kinetic sets for the purpose of determination of periodate in mixed (acetone-water) medium based upon the periodate oxidation of *o*-anisidine : [Mn^{II}] = 7.28 ×

Fig. 1. Determination of absorption maxima for the periodate oxidation of *o*-anisidine in acetone water medium. $[\text{NaIO}_4] = 2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{ANIS}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] = 7.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 5.0 % (v/v), temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 6.5.

$10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[\text{ANIS}] = 7.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), pH = 6.5, $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 490 \text{ nm}$, Temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $[\text{IO}_4^-]$ = unknown in the range of 3.82–101.72 $\mu\text{g/mL}$.

A definite volume of stock solution of Mn^{II} in water was mixed with calculated volumes of the stock solution of ANIS in acetone, acetone and water and stirred a little with the help of the pipette. This mixture and stock solution of NaIO_4 were then clamped in a thermostat at $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. After 25 min, a required amount of the periodate solution was added to the mixture and stirred to start the reaction. All additions were made in amounts calculated for maintaining the concentrations of different reagents

as mentioned above. Different sets were prepared in a similar manner varying the $[\text{IO}_4^-]$. The reaction mixture was transferred to the cuvette of double beam spectrophotometer immediately after start of reaction. The desired temperature was maintained in spectrophotometer cell also. The absorbance was recorded after repeated intervals of 30 s. The absorbance vs time plots were then made for different sets. The initial rates $[(dA/dt)_{30}]$ were evaluated after 30 s from the start of the reaction by applying plane mirror method on the absorbance vs time plots. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were found by Guggenheim's method³⁹. Using the method of least squares, linear calibration curves were obtained. Type

'A', type 'B', type 'C', type 'D', type 'E' and type 'F' plots were obtained in terms of A_{150} or A_{180} or A_{210} or A_{240} or initial rate or k_{obs} vs $[IO_4^-]$ plots respectively

(Figs. 2 and 3). Here A_{150} or A_{180} or A_{210} or A_{240} are the absorbance values after 150, 180, 210 and 240 s from the start of reaction respectively.

Fig. 2. Calibration curves in terms of absorbance vs $[IO_4^-]$ plots at $[ANIS] = 7.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Mn^{II}] = 7.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = $35.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 6.5, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), $\lambda_{max} = 490 \text{ nm}$.

Fig. 3. Calibration curves in terms of initial rate or pseudo-first order rate constant vs $[IO_4^-]$ plot at $[ANIS] = 7.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[Mn^{II}] = 7.28 \times 10^{-6} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, temp. = $35.0 \pm 0 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, pH = 6.5, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), $\lambda_{max} = 490 \text{ nm}$.

[IO₄⁻] may be determined in aqueous solutions and water samples by mixing the sample with calculated quantity of ANIS and acetone and starting the reaction by adding NaIO₄ followed by noting the absorbance of reaction mixture at different desired times as described above, or evaluating initial rate in terms of (dA/dt)₃₀ at a desired time by plane mirror method as discussed above. After it, different calibration curves may be used for determination of [IO₄⁻] in µg/ml.

Effect of interferrants :

The method is not applicable in presence of most of the aromatic amines/anilines. The method may be used in presence of the ions like Na⁺, K⁺, NO₂⁻, ClO₄²⁻, NO₃⁻ and SO₄²⁻ as they do not interfere in present case. However, the metals like Ag, As, B, Co, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mo, Ni, Pb, Sb, Se, U, and Zn are expected to interfere in this method. Therefore, a pretreatment is required for separating/precipitating/masking these ions before undertaking the proposed method. For this purpose, H₂S may be passed in presence of 0.3 M H⁺ solution, followed by filtration and boiling off H₂S. After it, a dilute alkaline solution of α-nitroso-β-naphthol should be added and again the solution should be filtered³⁶. Thereafter, the solution should be neutralized and the present method be applied. Fe may be removed by precipitation using basic formate method^{37,38}. In absence of the above given interferrants, the proposed method may successfully be used for the determination of microgram quantities of [IO₄⁻] in water samples.

Results and discussion

The reaction under consideration is already reported⁴⁰ to be first order in each reactant and catalyst with rate-pH profile showing a maximum at pH = 6.5 and reaction rate decreasing with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium. The reaction is not influenced by free radical scavengers and the main product of the reaction is methoxy-1,4-benzoquinone. The stoichiometry is 1 mol ANIS : 2 moles periodate for the initial part of reaction as given by the equation,

The rate law can be given by eq. (1),

$$d[\text{C}]/dt = k_{\text{cat}} [\text{ANIS}]_0 [\text{IO}_4^-]_0 [\text{Mn}^{\text{II}}] \quad (2)$$

where *k*_{cat} is the rate constant. [IO₄⁻]₀ and [ANIS]₀ represent respectively, the initial concentration of periodate and substrate.

As already reported by us⁴⁰, the probable mechanism based on kinetic and other studies, is as follows :

In steps (3–6), [C₁], [C₂], [C₃] and [C₄] are intermediates, out of which [C₄] appears to undergo very slow reorganization/hydrolysis to yield the reaction product, C₅.

In the mechanism for simplicity, H₄IO₆⁻ has been written as IO₄⁻. The formation of intermediates [C₁] and [C₂] in a rapid step having low values of equilibrium constants, K₁ and K₂, is assumed in the proposed gross mechanism. The catalytic role of Mn²⁺ appears to be due to the formation of a ternary complex, [(ANIS)Mn(H₄IO₆)]⁺, in which Mn acts as a conduit for electron transfer. High negative value of entropy of activation and the effect of dielectric constant on the reaction rate that support the solvation effects operating, as well as the formation of a charged intermediate complex C₂ by the attack of IO₄⁻ on the nitrogen of anilino group due to stabilization of positive charge on aniline nitrogen, have already been reported for the uncatalyzed/catalyzed periodate oxidation of aromatic amines^{32–33,40}.

Some of the characteristics of calibration curves can be presented in the form of equations of straight line as follows :

$$A_{150} = 2.18 \times 10^{-2} + 3.44 \times 10^{-3} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{i})$$

$$A_{180} = 2.92 \times 10^{-2} + 3.74 \times 10^{-3} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{ii})$$

$$A_{210} = 3.59 \times 10^{-2} + 4.00 \times 10^{-3} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{iii})$$

$$A_{240} = 4.16 \times 10^{-2} + 4.06 \times 10^{-3} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{iv})$$

Table 1. Characteristics of various types of calibration curves for the proposed method

[ANIS] = 7.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, [Mn^{II}] = 7.28×10^{-6} mol dm⁻³, temp. = 35.0 ± 0.1 °C, pH = 6.5, acetone = 5.0% (v/v), λ_{\max} = 490 nm

Parameter	'A' Plot	'B' Plot	'C' Plot	'D' Plot	'E' Plot (dA/dt) ₃₀	'F' Plot (k_{obs})
Beer's law limits (µg/mL)	3.82–101.72	3.82–101.72	3.82–101.72	3.82–101.72	3.82–101.72	3.82–101.72
Sandell's sensitivity (µg cm ⁻²)	0.239	0.198	0.179	0.174	–	–
Slope × 10 ³ absorbance units µg ⁻¹ cm ³	3.44	3.74	4.00	4.06	2.88×10^{-2}	7.02×10^{-2}
Intercept × 10 ³ absorbance units µg ⁻¹ cm ³	21.75	29.22	35.85	41.60	2.50×10^{-2}	2.29
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.9997	0.9997	0.9995	0.9995	0.9995	0.9989
Coefficient of determination (<i>r</i> ²)	0.9994	0.9995	0.9991	0.9990	0.9990	0.9979
' <i>t</i> ' (at 0.01 significance level)	7.2315	7.4132	7.5407	7.7135	6.6550	10.4621
Relative standard deviation (%) (from six determinations)	1.6734	0.4823	0.3676	0.0913	0.5030	2.91
Recovery (%)	99.81	99.69	99.89	99.95	100	99.70

$$(dA/dt)_{30} = 2.50 \times 10^{-5} + 2.88 \times 10^{-5} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{v})$$

$$k_{\text{obs}} = 2.29 \times 10^{-3} + 7.02 \times 10^{-5} [\text{IO}_4^-] \quad (\text{vi})$$

In eqs. (i)-(iv), the values of intercept and slope are in absorbance units and absorbance units µg⁻¹ mL respectively while these are absorbance units s⁻¹ and mL µg⁻¹ s⁻¹ in eqs. (v)-(vi). The [IO₄⁻] are in µg/mL.

Various characteristics of the calibration curves indicate reasonable sensitivity, percentage recovery, and correlation in the range of 3.82–101.72 µg/mL as given in Table 1. Value of Sandell's sensitivity suggests that a change in absorbance by 0.001 units is expected on changing the concentration of IO₄⁻ by 0.174–0.239 µg/mL. Further, on changing concentration of IO₄⁻ by 1 µg/mL, the value of k_{obs} will change by 7.02×10^{-5} in 1 s. This change is quite satisfactory and can be easily detected by using the methods under consideration. The correlation coefficient (*r*) is in the range 0.9989 to 0.9997 which indicates the high precision involved in the determination and almost perfect correlation of the data. The value of coefficient of determination (*r*²) suggests that 99.79 to 99.95% change in the value of absorbance or (dA/dt)_i or k_{obs} is caused by IO₄⁻ and the rest 0.05 to 0.21% is the effect of unknown factors. The values of '*t*' at 0.01 significance level, as calculated for the calibration curves, are much higher than the tabulated critical value at 1% significance level. This suggests that there are less than

1% chances of error in drawing conclusions. The standard deviation is within reasonable limits. Percentage recovery on the basis of six parallel determinations is 99.69 to 100%.

A comparison of the developed method with some of the reported methods reveals that lower detection limits and linear range of concentrations are available for estimation of periodate by using some of the already reported methods^{2-4,8-16}. However, all of these methods require lengthy pre-concentration and complex pretreatment of the samples and require the not-readily available facilities.

The volumetric titration based methods for periodate determination^{1,5-7}, claim the applicable concentration range between 0.4 µg/mL to micrograms and the detection limits as well as the sensitivity of the methods have not been worked out. The applicability of these methods is questionable as personnel errors are expected to occur in these methods. Less than 95.5 µg amounts of periodate are claimed to be determined by using potentiometric titrations². There is no range available for periodate determination using IR spectroscopy³. Our method is comparable and sometimes better in terms of wider linear range of concentration applicable and better sensitivity than other methods^{4,8-15} based on the techniques like flow injection, spectrofluorometric flow injection, chemiluminescence,

fluorescence measurements, static and flow injection voltammetry, SDME (Single drop micro extraction under solution immersion) and HS-SDME (Head space Single drop micro extraction under solution immersion). The Sandell's sensitivity of 0.174–0.239 µg/mL in our method is better than all methods available except the method based on fluorescence quenching¹⁴ and a recently reported method based on the use of L-cysteine-CdTe/ZnAs quantum dots as selective fluorescent probes¹⁶.

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